

Yuan Dao bian

also known as "Dispute over the 'Origin of the Way'", "Critique of the 'Origin of the Way'"

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Entry tags: Religious Group, Confucian Classic, Text, Chinese Buddhist text, Chan Buddhist text, Chinese Daoist Text, Chinese Religion

The "Yuan Dao bian" 原道辨 (Dispute over the "Origin of the Way") is a short essay composed by Song Emperor Xiaozong (r. 1162-1189) in 1178 or 1179. It challenges Han Yu's 韓愈 (768-824) "Yuan Dao" (Origin of the Way), an authoritative Confucian text at that time, and disagrees with Han's claim that Confucianism is incompatible with and superior to Daoism and Buddhism. Alternatively, the "Yuan Dao bian" argues that the Three Teachings of Confucianism, Buddhism, and Daoism derive from one origin but become compartmentalized due to their different functions. Xiaozong summarizes the capacities of the Three Teachings in one statement "Cultivate the mind with Buddhism, nourish the body with Daoism, and govern the world with Confucianism" 以佛修心以道養生以儒治世. The "Yuan Dao bian" resulted from Xiaozong's intellectual interest in Linji 臨濟 Chan Buddhism. In the second half of the twelfth century, Linji masters, especially Dahui Zonggao 大慧宗杲 (1089-1163), propagated among political elites the idea that the Three Teachings derived from one origin. Xiaozong incorporated this view into his essay and thus approved the Buddhist way of explaining the relationship among the Three Teachings. However, Xiaozong went further to argue that none of the concepts in the Three Teachings could completely represent the ultimate Dao because they were names that sages were forced to use when they established their teachings. In this regard, Xiaozong viewed the Dao as an abstract and universal truth that any language would fail to explain, and the Three Teachings as imperfect but necessary instruments of the Dao. Committed Confucian literati reacted strongly to the "Yuan Dao bian." Soon after Xiaozong wrote the essay, Shi Hao 史浩 (1106-1194), then Court Lecturer, advised the emperor to moderate his wording and show respect to the renowned Confucian Han Yu. In 1188, Zhu Xi 朱熹 (1130-1200), then leader of the Daoxue (Learning of the Way) Confucian fellowship, complained to Xiaozong that the essay ranked Confucianism the lowest and argued that his Daoxue Confucian program would be sufficient for the emperor to manage the mind, the body, and the world. There are two extant versions of the "Yuan Dao bian," one preserved in Shi Hao's collected works and the other in the Linji Buddhist monk Zhongwen Xiaoying's 仲溫曉瑩 (c. 1120-?) Yunwo jitan 雲臥紀譚 (Records and Discussions from Reclining on Clouds). The two versions are mostly the same except for the endings. The ending in Shi's version criticizes Han Yu for overemphasizing differences among the Three Teachings. The ending in Xiaoying's version implies that Xiaozong is a sage who can homogenize (tong 同) the Three Teachings. The Buddhist ending circulated under Xiaozong's reign demonstrates that Xiaozong attempted to create his own religion, in which he was both the political and the religious leader. The "Yuan Dao bian" had significant impacts on later discussions about the Three Teachings and was among the predecessors of the notion of "Uniting the Three Teachings into One" (Sanjiao heyi 三教合一).

Date Range: 1178 CE - 1179 CE

Region: Southern Song (1127-1279 CE)

Region tags: China, Song China

Approximate area of the Southern Song.

Status of Readership:

✓ Elite

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Shi Hao 史浩 (1106-1194). Maofeng zhenyin manlu 鄮峰真隱漫錄. In Yingyin wenyuange sikuquanshu 景印文淵閣四庫全書. 10. Taipei: Taiwan shangwu yinshuguan, 1983.
- Source 2: Zhongwen Xiaoying 仲溫曉瑩 (c. 1120-?). Yunwo jitan 雲臥記譚. In Shinsan Dai nihon zokuzōkyō 新纂大日本續藏經. No. 1610. Tokyo: Kokushokankōkai, 1975-1976.
- Source 3: Li Xinchuan 李心傳 (1167-1244). "'Yuan Dao bian' yiming 'Sanjiao lun'" 原道辨易名三教論. In Jianyan yilai chaoye zaji 建炎以來朝野雜記. yi.3.544. Beijing: Zhonghua shuju, 2000.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: N/A

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

- Source 1 URL: https://cbetaonline.dila.edu.tw/zh/X1610_002
- Source 1 Description: Zhongwen Xiaoying's version of the "Yuan Dao bian" from CBETA.

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

– Written

Inked

– with Ink

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Other textile: Silk or paper

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– Other [specify]: Field doesn't know.

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

– Other [specify]: Emperor Xiaozong might have revised the ending of the "Yuan Dao bian" after receiving

Shi Hao's criticism.

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– No

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– No

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– No

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– Yes

↳ Are the authors/copyists/engravers paid by the polity?

– No

Notes: The author is the emperor.

↳ Does the polity provide financial support to religious infrastructure involved with textual production?

– Yes

Notes: The government under Emperor Xiaozong had a close tie with Linji Chan Buddhism, especially Dahui Zonggao and his disciples. These Buddhist clerics had a significant impact on the formation of Xiaozong's view in his "Yuan Dao bian." Because of this relationship, the Song government financially supported many Linji monasteries in Jing Mountain 徑山 near the Southern Song capital Lin'an 臨安 (modern Hangzhou).

↳ Are the leaders of the polity and the religion the same figure?

– Yes

Notes: Song Emperor Xiaozong, leader of the polity, was under Buddhist influence when he created the text. But he morphed his contemporary Buddhist view toward interrelations between the Three Teachings into a new one entirely under his control. Precisely in that sense, he was creating his own religion, regardless of how successful it was, in which Xiaozong was

both the political and the religious leader.

Reference: Li, Jiangnan. "Bitter Compromise: Buddhist Discourse on the Three Teachings". *The Making of Imperial Religion: State and the Three Teachings in Song China (960-1279)*. Ph.D. dissertation, Arizona State University, 2023.

↳ Are political officials involved in the support of textual production?

– Yes

Notes: Palace eunuchs, such as Gan Bing 甘昺 (fl. late 12th century), played an important role in liaising between the emperor and the text's recipients. Therefore, palace eunuchs were involved in the textual circulation and possibly the production of the "Yuan Dao bian." But scholar-officials who were committed to Confucianism, especially Zhu Xi, opposed producing and circulating the "Yuan Dao bian."

↳ Are political officials and religious officials otherwise overlapping institutional networks?

– No

↳ Does the polity enforce religious observance according to text or texts?

– No

↳ Is the polity legal code derived from religious text(s) in question?

– No

↳ Is preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax exemption) present in the polity to support the text(s)...

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are religious specialists present/in charge of the production of the text or copies of the text?

– Yes

Notes: Since Emperor Xiaozong was under the influence of Chan Buddhist clerics of the Linji school, preserving and circulating the "Yuan Dao bian" became beneficial to Linji masters and later Buddhist compilers. Thus, 12th-century and 13th-century Buddhists actively included this text in their writings. These Linji Buddhists are the religious specialists that I address in the following questions.

↳ Present full-time?

– No

↳ Present part-time?

– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists of a specific sex/gender?

– Yes

Notes: Buddhist clerics involved in textual production were predominantly male.

↳ Are the religious specialists of a specific ethnicity?

– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists of a specific class/caste?

– Yes

↳ Is this class/caste based on a cultural status?

– Yes

↳ Is this class/caste based on socioeconomic status?

– Yes

Notes: Most of the Buddhist masters who helped preserve and circulate the text were associated with state-regulated monasteries.

↳ Are the religious specialists dedicated to the place for life?

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system?

– Yes

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy?

– I don't know

↳ Are there regulations/provisions for living spaces of religious specialists?

– Yes

Notes: State-regulated Buddhist monasteries.

↳ Are there regulations/provisions for training spaces of religious specialists?

– Yes

↳ Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of a body of religious

specialists?

– Yes

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– Yes

Notes: The text with the ending in Zhongwen Xiaoying's version was included in the 13th-century monumental Buddhist history, the Fozu tongji 佛祖統紀 (Comprehensive History of the Buddhist Patriarchs).

↳ Is there a culture of oral recitation?

– No

↳ Is there a story associated with the origins of scripture?

– No

↳ Are the scriptures alterable?

– Yes

↳ Do the practitioners generally consider the scripture open to alteration?

– No

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting scriptures?

– No

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures?

– No

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures?

– No

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– No

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– Field doesn't know

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– No

Notes: Emperor Xiaozong composed the "Yuan Dao bian" and the view therein does not dovetail with anyone of Buddhism, Daoism, and Confucianism despite the Buddhist influence. Instead, the "Yuan Dao bian" aims to enhance the authority of the emperor to manage the Three Teachings. Since the emperor was the ultimate political leader and was claiming the role of the ultimate religious leader, he needed not to recruit new members actively. Religious specialists who desired imperial sponsorship would voluntarily subscribe to this view.

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– No

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– Field doesn't know

Is there material significance to the text?

– Yes

Notes: The original version of the "Yuan Dao bian" was written either on a particular kind of paper or silk used by the emperor. Therefore, the recipients of the text would immediately know that the piece was endorsed by the highest authority of the state.

↳ Is it visible?

– Yes

↳ Is it hidden?

– No

↳ Can it be touched?

– Yes

↳ Does touching the text during ritual have a specific function?

– No

↳ Does the material significance have an esoteric function?

– No

↳ Does the text serve a protective function?

– No

↳ Does the text serve a healing function?

– No

↳ Does the text serve a cleansing function?

– No

↳ Does the text serve as a form of expiation?

– No

↳ Does the text serve as an incantation?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Has the materiality of the text been altered?

– Yes

↳ Specify

– Specify: The text was originally in the form of a manuscript and then was included in Buddhist compilations and Shi Hao's collected works. As a result, its form developed from manuscript to printed books.

↳ Are there debates about whether or not altering the materiality of the text is acceptable?

– No

↳ Other important aspects of materiality with regard to the text?

– No

↳ Are there material substance that commonly accompany the text?

Please specify the substances in the sub-questions

– No

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– Yes

↳ Are multiple versions viewed as proper?

– Yes

↳ If multiple versions are proper, is there a differentiation among versions by any means?

– Yes

Notes: The version by the Confucian literatus Shi Hao describes the exchanges between Emperor Xiaozong and Shi about the "Yuan Dao bian." It emphasizes how Shi successfully persuaded Xiaozong to revise the last part of the "Yuan Dao bian." The version preserved by Buddhist master Zhongwen Xiaowen preserves an ending in which Xiaozong claims he is the sage who can homogenize (tong 同) the Three Teachings.

↳ Age of extant version of text?

– Yes

Notes: According to Nap-yin Lau's research, Emperor Xiaozong wrote the essay between 1178 and 1179. Shi Hao's collected works, *Maofeng zhenyin manlu* 賀峰真隱漫錄 (Leisurely Records by the True Recluse at Mao Peak), and Xiaoying's *Yunwo jitan* were respectively completed around 1194 and 1188. The two versions of the "Yuan Dao bian" could have been included their works around those times.

Reference: Lau, Nap-Yin. "The Absolutist Reign of Sung Hsiao-tsung". Ph.D. dissertation, Princeton University, 1986.

Reference: Li, Jiangnan. "Bitter Compromise: Buddhist Discourse on the Three Teachings". *The Making of Imperial Religion: State and the Three Teachings in Song China (960-1279)*. Ph.D. dissertation, Arizona State University, 2023.

↳ Content of text?

– Yes

↳ Ritual purpose of text?

– No

↳ Is there debate about which version is proper?

– No

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– Yes

↳ Is there a sense of canonization?

– No

Notes: Although Shi Hao and Zhongwen Xiaoying had their political and religious agendas by preserving their versions of the "Yuan Dao bian," they did not intend to canonize their writings.

↳ Is the text part of a series of volumes?

– No

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Yes

↳ Cultural with religious implications?

– Yes

Notes: The "Yuan Dao bian" belongs to the literary tradition in which the emperor creates writings to discuss religions, often one or more of the Three Teachings. This tradition became prominent in early medieval China and continued into the Song dynasty. For example, Emperor Wu of Liang (502-549) once wrote the "Hui sanjiao shi" 會三教詩 (A Poem Bring Together the Three Teachings) to delineate how he in different life stages sought help from Confucianism, Daoism, and then Buddhism.

Reference: Tian, Xiaofei. Beacon Fire and Shooting Star: The Literary Culture of the Liang (502-557). Leiden: Brill, 2020.

https://books.google.com/books/about/Beacon_Fire_and_Shooting_Star.html?hl=&id=yfcFEAAAQBAJ.

↳ Behavioral literature?

– I don't know

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: N/A

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

–Other [specify]: N/A

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– Yes

↳ Spirit-Mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other parts?

– Yes

Notes: The "Yuan Dao bian" assigns each of the Three Teachings one function—use Buddhism to cultivate the mind, Daoism to nourish/manage the body, and Confucianism to govern the world. "Use Daoism to nourish/manage the body" is expressed differently in Shi Hao and Xiaoying's versions. In Shi's version, the statement can be literally translated into "use to Daoism to nourish life" (yi Dao yangsheng 以道養生). But "life" (sheng) here should refer to one's physical body. In Xiaoying's version, the statement can be rendered literally as "use Laozi's [teaching] to manage one's body" (yi Lao zhishen 以老治身). Despite the difference, it is clear that Xiaozong differentiated mind from physical body.

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body?

– Yes

↳ Other spirit-body relationship?

– No

↳ Within conceptions of the mind: are there distinct notions of psychological states or aggregates?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Do practitioners engage in debates about mind-body dualism?

– No

↳ Are debates framed in other ways?

– Yes

Notes: The debates were mainly about whether or not Buddhism and Daoism could be sources of cultivating heart-mind and body. Xiaozong disagreed with Han Yu's view that only Confucianism possessed the correct Dao and thus assigned mind and body respectively to Buddhism and Daoism. Shi Hao and Zhu Xi opposed Xiaozong's essay and argued that Confucianism, especially its ideas of "rectifying the heart-mind" (zhengxin 正心) and "cultivating the body" (xiushen 修身) in the Great Learning (Daxue 大學), already had what necessary for one's mind-body cultivation.

Reference: Li, Jiangnan. "Bitter Compromise: Buddhist Discourse on the Three Teachings". The Making of Imperial Religion: State and the Three Teachings in Song China (960-1279). Ph.D. dissertation, Arizona State University, 2023.

Reference: Li, Jiangnan. "Confronting Buddhism and Daoism at the Imperial Court: A Comparison Between Wang Anshi (1021-1086) and Zhu Xi (1130-1200)". The Making of Imperial Religion: State and the Three Teachings in Song China (960-1279). Ph.D. dissertation, Arizona State University, 2023.

↳ Do practitioners distinguish between a corporeal body and an incorporeal soul or spirit?

– Yes

↳ Are there other sides or features of the debate?

– No

↳ What are historical mainstream and minority positions?

– Field doesn't know

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– No

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– No

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– No

Previously human spirits are present

– No

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– No

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Are other categories of beings present?

– Other [specify]: Śākyamuni, Laozi, and Confucius were mentioned in the "Yuan Dao bian" as historical figures, more specifically sages who established their teachings according to the Dao.

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– No

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– Yes

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

Notes: Please note all virtues mentioned in the "Yuan Dao bian" are considered labels that sages were forced to give when they established their teachings. In this regard, these virtues are manifestations of the ultimate Dao. But none of them can completely represent the Dao.

↳ Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity

– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle)

– No

↳ Courage (generic)

- No
- ↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence
 - Yes
- ↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance
 - Yes
- ↳ Generosity/charity
 - No
- ↳ Selflessness/selfless giving
 - Yes
- ↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude
 - Yes
- ↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity
 - No
- ↳ Respectfulness/courtesy
 - Yes
- ↳ Familial obedience/filial piety
 - No
- ↳ Fidelity/loyalty
 - No
- ↳ Cooperation
 - No
- ↳ Independence/creativity/freedom
 - No
- ↳ Moderation/frugality

– Yes

↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience

– Yes

↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence

– No

↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative

– No

↳ Strength (physical)

– No

↳ Power/status/nobility

– No

↳ Humility/modesty

– Yes

↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity

– Yes

↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness

– No

↳ Optimism/hope

– No

↳ Gratitude/thankfulness

– No

↳ Reverence/awe/wonder

– No

↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion

– Yes

↳ Wisdom/understanding

– Yes

↳ Discernment/intelligence

– Yes

↳ Beauty/attractiveness

– No

↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness

– No

↳ Other important virtues

– No

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– No

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– Yes

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– No

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– No

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– An empire

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– A band

Notes: Buddhists and Confucians reproduced the text in accordance with their respective interests.

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– An empire

Notes: At the early stage of the textual distribution, inner court personnel, especially palace eunuchs, played an important role in sending the text to its recipients.

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– No

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– Yes

Notes: The "Yuan Dao bian" educates its readers on governing the world with Confucianism, which was a predominantly male achievement in traditional China.

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– Yes

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– Yes

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– No

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Yuan Dao bian, Schlütter, Morten. "China's Three Teachings and the Thought of Emperor Xiaozong (r. 1162-1189)". *Occasional Papers* 6 (1990): 151-61.

Reference: Yuan Dao bian, Lau, Nap-Yin. "The Absolutist Reign of Sung Hsiao-tsung". Ph.D. dissertation, Princeton University, 1986.

Reference: Yuan Dao bian, Brook, Timothy. "Rethinking Syncretism: The Unity of the Three Teachings and Their Joint Worship in Late-imperial China". *Journal of Chinese Religions* 21, no. 1 (January 1993): 13-44. <https://doi.org/10.1179/073776993805307448>.

Reference: Yuan Dao bian, Li, Jiangnan. "Bitter Compromise: Buddhist Discourse on the Three Teachings". *The Making of Imperial Religion: State and the Three Teachings in Song China (960-1279)*. Ph.D. dissertation, Arizona State University, 2023.

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Entry/Answer References

Reference: Yes, Tian, Xiaofei. *Beacon Fire and Shooting Star: The Literary Culture of the Liang (502-557)*. Leiden: Brill, 2020. https://books.google.com/books/about/Beacon_Fire_and_Shooting_Star.html?hl=&id=yfcFEAAAQBAJ.

Reference: Yes, Lau, Nap-Yin. "The Absolutist Reign of Sung Hsiao-tsung". Ph.D. dissertation, Princeton University, 1986.

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